

Supplementary Material S1: Complete Set of Association Rules Generated by the Entropy-Guided SOM-CBA Framework

This supplementary material presents the complete set of association rules generated by the entropy-guided hybrid SOM-CBA framework described in the main manuscript. The rules were extracted from high-entropy neurons identified during the entropy analysis stage, corresponding to regions with greater class overlap and diagnostic uncertainty.

Each rule represents interpretable relationships between hematological variables and the predicted diagnostic class (COVID-19 positive or negative). The inclusion of the full rule set aims to enhance transparency, reproducibility, and interpretability of the proposed explainable artificial intelligence model, allowing detailed inspection of the decision logic derived from routine blood count data.

Rules_SOM_2x2

Neuron	Rule_ID	Rule	Class	Support	Confidence
4	[1]	Hematocrit = $[-\infty, 376]$	0	0.50	1.00
3	[1]	Leukocytes = $[4.64e + 03, 1.05e + 04)$, Eosinophils.Absoluto = $[85,765)$, Basophils.Absoluto = $[29, \infty)$, Monocytes.Absoluto = $[215,645)$	0	0.24	0.85
3	[2]	Platelets = $[2.06e + 05, \infty)$, Leukocytes = $[4.64e + 03, 1.05e + 04)$, Basophils.Absoluto = $[29, \infty)$, Monocytes.Absoluto = $[215,645)$	1	0.25	0.84
3	[3]	Lymphocytes.Absoluto = $[1.32e + 03, 7.48e + 03)$, Leukocytes = $[4.64e + 03, 1.05e + 04)$, Basophils.Absoluto = $[29, \infty)$, Monocytes.Absoluto = $[215,645)$	1	0.28	0.84
3	[4]	Platelets = $[2.06e + 05, \infty)$, Lymphocytes.Absoluto = $[1.32e + 03, 7.48e + 03)$, Basophils.Absoluto = $[29, \infty)$, Monocytes.Absoluto = $[215,645)$	1	0.27	0.83

Rules_SOM_3x3

Neuron	Rule_ID	Rule	Class	Support	Confidence
1	[1]	Hematocrit = $[-\infty, 264]$	0	0.333	1.00
1	[2]	Eosinophils.Absoluto = $[1.07e +05, \infty]$	1	0.333	1.00
3	[1]	Leukocytes= $[-\infty, 9.7e + 03)$	1	0.75	1.00
4	[1]	Mean.corpuscular.hemoglobi n.concentration.MCHCs= $[-\infty, 171)$	0	0.333	1.00
6	[1]	Lymphocytes.Absoluto= $[-\text{Inf}, 1.35e+03),$ Basophils.Absoluto= $[-\text{Inf}, 26)$	1	0.24	0.81
7	[1]	Monocytes.Absoluto= $[-\text{Inf}, 1e +04)$	1	0.24	0.81
8	[1]	Lymphocytes.Absoluto= $[1.22 e+03, 1.86e+03),$ Leukocytes= $[4.64e+03, 1.05e +04),$ Basophils.Absoluto= $[29, \text{Inf}],$ Monocytes.Absoluto= $[215, 655)$	1	0.10	0.86
8	[2]	Platelets= $[2.06e+05, \text{Inf}],$ Lymphocytes.Absoluto= $[1.22 e+03, 1.86e+03),$ Basophils.Absoluto= $[29, \text{Inf}],$ Monocytes.Absoluto= $[215, 655)$	0	0.10	0.84
8	[3]	Leukocytes= $[4.64e+03, 1.05e +04),$ Basophils.Absoluto= $[29, \text{Inf}],$ Eosinophils.Absoluto= $[85, 1.03e+03),$ Monocytes.Absoluto= $[215, 655)$	0	0.26	0.84
8	[4]	Lymphocytes.Absoluto= $[1.22 e+03, 1.86e+03),$ Basophils.Absoluto= $[29, \text{Inf}],$ Eosinophils.Absoluto= $[85, 1.03e+03),$ Monocytes.Absoluto= $[215, 655)$	0	0.09	0.84
8	[5]	Lymphocytes.Absoluto= $[1.22 e+03, 1.86e+03),$ Leukocytes= $[4.64e+03, 1.05e +04),$ Basophils.Absoluto= $[29, \text{Inf}],$ Eosinophils.Absoluto= $[85, 1.03e+03)$	0	0.09	0.84

8	[6]	Platelets=[2.06e+05, Inf], Leukocytes=[4.64e+03,1.05e+04), Basophils.Absoluto=[29, Inf], Monocytes.Absoluto=[215,655)	0	0.26	0.84
8	[7]	Lymphocytes.Absoluto=[1.22e+03,1.86e+03), Leukocytes=[4.64e+03,1.05e+04), Eosinophils.Absoluto=[85,1.03e+03), Monocytes.Absoluto=[215,655)	0	0.10	0.84
8	[8]	Platelets=[2.06e+05, Inf], Basophils.Absoluto=[29, Inf], Eosinophils.Absoluto=[85,1.03e+03), Monocytes.Absoluto=[215,655)	0	0.23	0.84
8	[9]	Platelets=[2.06e+05, Inf], Lymphocytes.Absoluto=[1.86e+03,7.48e+03), Basophils.Absoluto=[29, Inf], Monocytes.Absoluto=[215,655)	0	0.18	0.84
8	[10]	Lymphocytes.Absoluto=[1.86e+03,7.48e+03), Leukocytes=[4.64e+03,1.05e+04), Basophils.Absoluto=[29, Inf], Eosinophils.Absoluto=[85,1.03e+03)	0	0.22	0.83
8	[11]	Platelets=[2.06e+05, Inf], Lymphocytes.Absoluto=[1.86e+03,7.48e+03), Basophils.Absoluto=[29, Inf], Eosinophils.Absoluto=[85,1.03e+03)	0	0.21	0.83
8	[12]	Leukocytes=[4.64e+03,1.05e+04), Basophils.Absoluto=[29, Inf], Monocytes.Absoluto=[215,655)	0	0.31	0.83
8	[13]	Platelets=[2.06e+05, Inf], Basophils.Absoluto=[29, Inf], Monocytes.Absoluto=[215,655)	0	0.30	0.83
8	[14]	Platelets=[2.06e+05, Inf], Leukocytes=[4.64e+03,1.05e+04), Basophils.Absoluto=[29, Inf], Eosinophils.Absoluto=[85,1.03e+03)	0	0.27	0.83
8	[15]	Lymphocytes.Absoluto=[1.86e+03,7.48e+03),	0	0.18	0.83

		Basophils.Absoluto=[29, Inf], Eosinophils.Absoluto=[85,1.0 3e+03), Monocytes.Absoluto=[215,65 5)			
8	[16]	Basophils.Absoluto=[29, Inf], Eosinophils.Absoluto=[85,1.0 3e+03), Monocytes.Absoluto=[215,65 5)	0	0.29	0.83
8	[17]	Lymphocytes.Absoluto=[1.22 e+03,1.86e+03), Basophils.Absoluto=[29, Inf], Monocytes.Absoluto=[215,65 5)	0	0.12	0.82
8	[18]	Platelets=[2.06e+05, Inf], Lymphocytes.Absoluto=[1.86 e+03,7.48e+03), Leukocytes=[4.64e+03,1.05e +04), Basophils.Absoluto=[29, Inf]	0	0.23	0.82
8	[19]	Platelets=[2.06e+05, Inf], Lymphocytes.Absoluto=[1.22 e+03,1.86e+03), Eosinophils.Absoluto=[85,1.0 3e+03), Monocytes.Absoluto=[215,65 5)	0	0.10	0.82
8	[20]	Leukocytes=[4.64e+03,1.05e +04), Basophils.Absoluto=[29, Inf], Eosinophils.Absoluto=[85,1.0 3e+03)	0	0.32	0.82
8	[21]	Lymphocytes.Absoluto=[1.86 e+03,7.48e+03), Basophils.Absoluto=[29, Inf], Eosinophils.Absoluto=[85,1.0 3e+03)	0	0.24	0.82
8	[22]	Platelets=[2.06e+05, Inf], Lymphocytes.Absoluto=[1.86 e+03,7.48e+03), Basophils.Absoluto=[29, Inf]	0	0.25	0.82
8	[23]	Lymphocytes.Absoluto=[1.86 e+03,7.48e+03), Basophils.Absoluto=[29, Inf], Monocytes.Absoluto=[215,65 5)	0	0.21	0.82
8	[24]	Platelets=[2.06e+05, Inf], Leukocytes=[4.64e+03,1.05e +04), Eosinophils.Absoluto=[85,1.0 3e+03), Monocytes.Absoluto=[215,65 5)	0	0.26	0.82

8	[25]	Platelets=[2.06e+05, Inf], Basophils.Absoluto=[29, Inf], Eosinophils.Absoluto=[85, 1.0 3e+03)	0	0.31	0.82
8	[26]	Platelets=[2.06e+05, Inf], Lymphocytes.Absoluto=[1.22 e+03, 1.86e+03), Leukocytes=[4.64e+03, 1.05e +04), Basophils.Absoluto=[29, Inf]	0	0.09	0.82
8	[27]	Lymphocytes.Absoluto=[1.86 e+03, 7.48e+03), Leukocytes=[4.64e+03, 1.05e +04), Basophils.Absoluto=[29, Inf]	0	0.26	0.82
8	[28]	Lymphocytes.Absoluto=[1.22 e+03, 1.86e+03), Basophils.Absoluto=[29, Inf], Eosinophils.Absoluto=[85, 1.0 3e+03)	0	0.11	0.81
8	[29]	Lymphocytes.Absoluto=[1.22 e+03, 1.86e+03), Leukocytes=[4.64e+03, 1.05e +04), Eosinophils.Absoluto=[85, 1.0 3e+03)	0	0.12	0.81
8	[30]	Lymphocytes.Absoluto=[1.22 e+03, 1.86e+03), Leukocytes=[4.64e+03, 1.05e +04), Basophils.Absoluto=[29, Inf]	0	0.12	0.81
8	[31]	Leukocytes=[4.64e+03, 1.05e +04), Eosinophils.Absoluto=[85, 1.0 3e+03), Monocytes.Absoluto=[215, 65 5)	0	0.31	0.81
8	[32]	Lymphocytes.Absoluto=[1.22 e+03, 1.86e+03), Eosinophils.Absoluto=[85, 1.0 3e+03), Monocytes.Absoluto=[215, 65 5)	0	0.13	0.81
8	[33]	Platelets=[2.06e+05, Inf], Lymphocytes.Absoluto=[1.86 e+03, 7.48e+03), Leukocytes=[4.64e+03, 1.05e +04), Eosinophils.Absoluto=[85, 1.0 3e+03)	0	0.22	0.81
8	[34]	Basophils.Absoluto=[29, Inf], Monocytes.Absoluto=[215, 65 5)	0	0.36	0.81
8	[35]	Platelets=[2.06e+05, Inf], Leukocytes=[4.64e+03, 1.05e	0	0.33	0.81

		+04), Basophils.Absoluto=[29, Inf]			
8	[36]	Basophils.Absoluto=[29, Inf], Eosinophils.Absoluto=[85, 1.0 3e+03)	0	0.37	0.81
8	[37]	Lymphocytes.Absoluto=[1.86 e+03, 7.48e+03), Basophils.Absoluto=[29, Inf]	0	0.29	0.81
8	[38]	Platelets=[2.06e+05, Inf], Eosinophils.Absoluto=[85, 1.0 3e+03), Monocytes.Absoluto=[215, 65 5)	0	0.28	0.81
8	[39]	Lymphocytes.Absoluto=[1.86 e+03, 7.48e+03), Leukocytes=[4.64e+03, 1.05e +04), Eosinophils.Absoluto=[85, 1.0 3e+03)	0	0.26	0.80
8	[40]	Platelets=[2.06e+05, Inf], Lymphocytes.Absoluto=[1.86 e+03, 7.48e+03), Eosinophils.Absoluto=[85, 1.0 3e+03)	0	0.24	0.80
8	[41]	Platelets=[2.06e+05, Inf], Leukocytes=[4.64e+03, 1.05e +04), Eosinophils.Absoluto=[85, 1.0 3e+03)	0	0.32	0.80
8	[42]	Platelets=[2.06e+05, Inf], Basophils.Absoluto=[29, Inf]	0	0.38	0.80
8	[43]	Platelets=[2.06e+05, Inf], Lymphocytes.Absoluto=[1.22 e+03, 1.86e+03), Eosinophils.Absoluto=[85, 1.0 3e+03)	0	0.11	0.80
8	[44]	Platelets=[2.06e+05, Inf], Lymphocytes.Absoluto=[1.86 e+03, 7.48e+03), Leukocytes=[4.64e+03, 1.05e +04), Monocytes.Absoluto=[215, 65 5)	0	0.22	0.80